

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES ON THE CONTENT OF THE STATE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS.

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Scientists and specialists of the developed countries of the world are carrying out many scientific research works on conducting and improving physical education in general education schools in accordance with the requirements of the time. In particular, to find ways to improve the health and physical fitness of children, to increase their movement activity and to rationalize the curriculum of physical education classes, model descriptions aimed at improving extracurricular activities on physical education and various scientifically based methods have been developed that help to strengthen the health of students during the training. and put into practice.

In order to identify modern trends and gaps in knowledge, foreign scientific literature on the topic of the dissertation was extensively analyzed. In this, the greatest attention is paid to scientific materials from the USA, Great Britain, Australia and other European countries. Advanced scientific research on the problems is carried out in a number of foreign leading research institutions and higher education institutions specializing in physical education and sports, including Coventry University (Coventry University - Great Britain), University of Alberta (Canada) Southern Cross University (Southern Cross University) Cross University - Australia), Hungarian University of Sports Science (Hungary), Lithuanian Sports University (Lithuania), Beijing Sports University (People's Republic of China), Korea National Sports University (Korea National Sports University - Republic of Korea), Russian State University of Physical Education, Sports, Youth and Tourism (Russian Federation), Belarus State University of Physical Education (Republic of Belarus)¹.

The content of general education in the field of physical education requires in-depth study and scientific justification. According to a number of experts in the field, it is necessary to carry out a large amount of research on determining the content of the physical education process of young students, the existing problems in the field complicate practical work on improving the

¹ Balikina E.V., Baranov V.A. Physical education and sports in educational institutions: textbook. Moscow: Enlightenment, 2017. - 192 articles; Vidyakin M.V. Extracurricular work in physical education in primary school - M.: Corypheus, 2006. - 128 p.; Karelin V.V. Model of physical education of schoolchildren in a general education school. Moscow: Physical culture and sport, 2017. - 176 articles; Pashenko L.A., Melnikova E.A. Theory and methodology of physical education and sports. Moscow: Physical culture and sport, 2021. - 288 articles;

educational process of physical education in the system of general education schools. [7; 325-p.].

Monitoring the work of general education schools, analyzing school programs on physical education in our country and foreign countries, indicates that the modern theory defining the content and normative bases of the science of "Physical Education" in our republic during the years of independence has not been developed and requires improvement.

Until now, the definition of the content of "Physical education" subject in secondary schools has been carried out based on practical principles. Selection of software material is carried out taking into account the results of the expert method, which is confirmed by the great diversity of opinions, the large number of mutually exclusive changes, and the frequent exchange of basic assumptions.

It is worth saying that the analysis of the researches carried out on this problem showed the existence of a large number of fragments that did not provide an opportunity for deep methodological and conceptual understanding. Based on this, it becomes possible to implement goal-oriented measures to solve this problem.

Based on this, there is a need to determine the situation of this pedagogical problem and its methodological foundations that allow pedagogical analysis from the position of a necessary and objective approach to solving it.

The implementation of this issue consists of studying from the position of a systematic approach, which, in the general overview of the problem, involves the separation of key problems and the formation of a generally accepted point of view on them. and allows you to define its systematization.

It is desirable to increase the level of physical fitness in accordance with the individual characteristics and health status of students in general education schools. In order to achieve this goal, pedagogical corrections have been made to the content of the educational material provided for in the state program on physical education, taking into account the specific conditions of the region, the material and technical base of general education schools, and the physical fitness of students.

It includes improvement of students' physical qualities, review of software standards and strengthening of health. One of the most significant transformations in physical education is the formation of students to independently engage in physical exercises. At the same time, it is aimed at the development of basic physical abilities aimed at strengthening health and expanding the functional capabilities of the body.

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